

EFFICACY OF COMBINATION THERAPY USING NEBIVALOL AND TRIMETAZIDINE IN PATIENTS WITH ISOLATED SYSTOLIC HYPERTENSION AND STABLE ANGINA

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Objective: The aim of this study was to evaluate the efficacy of beta – blocker nebivalol alone or in combination with metabolic agent trimetazidine in patients with isolated systolic hypertension (ISH) and stable angina (SA).

Design and method: Forty eight patients with mild ISH, SA and documented coronary artery disease (CAD), aged 50 – 64 years, were randomly assigned to nebivalol -2.5 mg daily (group A-25 patients) and nebivalol 2.5 mg daily with trimetazidine MR 35 mg twice daily (group B-30 patients). Echocardiography and treadmill exercise tests were performed at baseline and after 6 months of therapy. The parameters of left ventricular (LV) hypertrophy were evaluated. Differences in the efficacy parameters were analysed using 2-tailed Student's t test for quantitative parameters. At baseline there were no significant differences between the groups.

Results: At the end of the study systolic BP was lowered in both groups to less than 140 mm Hg. LV mass index reduced from 153.7 ± 7.2 to 123.4 ± 3.2 g/m² with nebivalol and from 154.9 ± 7.2 to 122.3 ± 2.9 g/m² with nebivalol and trimetazidine MR in combination ($p < 0,05$ for both groups). At the end of the study time to 1 mm ST segment depression compared to baseline increased by 12.5 % in group A ($p < 0.01$) and by 16.7 % in group B ($p < 0,001$). Time to onset of angina increased by 8.3 % in group A ($p < 0.01$) and by 20.8 % in group B ($p < 0.001$). Maximum ST segment depression compared to baseline passed by 8.3 % in group A ($p < 0.01$) and by 16.6 % in group B ($p < 0.001$). Mean number of anginal attacks per week decreased by 25.0 % in group A ($p < 0.01$) and by 33.3 % in group B ($p < 0.001$). There was no significant difference between two groups for grade of anginal pain.

Conclusions: Therapy with beta-blocker induced qualitative antihypertensive effect and qualitative effect on the parameters of LV hypertrophy in patients with ISH and CAD. Combination treatment using beta-blocker and metabolic agent produced significant improvements in exercise stress tests and reduced clinical symptoms compared to beta-blocker alone.

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